

EVALUATION OF CRITICAL CARE NURSES COMPETENCE IN APPLICATION OF GLASGOW COMA SCALE (GCS); A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Background: The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) is a tool that requires knowledge in order to assess a patient's level of consciousness and identify any early signs of deterioration. Every aspect of nursing practice is built on the application of critical thinking along with expertise and understanding in GCS assessment. The purpose of this study was to ascertain what knowledge have nurses in critical care settings regarding the Glasgow Coma Scale. *Methods:* A quasi experimental study was conducted between July to December 2023 among 60 nurses working in the critical care settings of tertiary care hospitals of Islamabad using purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by using structured, self-administered pre and post questionnaire. *Results:* In the pre-test 25% nurses were having poor knowledge, 61.69% nurses were having average knowledge and 13.31% nurses were having good knowledge regarding GCS in pretest questionnaire. After giving teaching session regarding GCS knowledge, 20% nurses were having good knowledge and 80% nurses were having excellent knowledge in the post test. *Conclusions:* In the pre-test that majority of nurses had unsatisfactory level of knowledge regarding GCS. However, after teaching session regarding on the GCS knowledge this level was satisfactory which was assessed in post-test.

INTRODUCTION

The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), designed in 1974, is a tool developed by Graham Teasdale and Bryan J. as a mean of expressing the degree of consciousness experienced by patients suffering from acute or severe brain injury. It is the gold standard for diagnosing neurologic impairment in all acute medical and trauma patients. It is imperative that nurses comprehend its function and usage to the fullest. The first step in utilizing the scale correctly is to determine which patients need to be scored. The progress degree of awareness, which assessed the patient's ability to open their eyes, move their limbs, and vocalize, is something that nurses who work with these patients must understand. It is acquired by verbal and/or painful stimulation in addition to the

observation of spontaneous activities¹. Among all the neurological patients, it is the most accurate and sensitive indicator. Because it is systematic and obvious assessment medical practitioners can reach a consensus regarding the patient's situation². The research literature demonstrates that, in addition to expertise and education, GCS assessment standardization is critical to guaranteeing assessment accuracy³. Nurses must be able to reliably determine each patient's level of awareness in order for the medical team to quickly decide on the best course of action and avoid irreversible harm to the patient⁴. Nurses who work in settings where these individuals are cared for must be capable of performing GCS assessments. In these patients, the scoring will

identify early decline⁵. To use and recognize changes in a patient's awareness, nurses need to fully understand the GCS. GCS assessments must be performed by nurses who work in the critical settings where these individuals are cared for⁶. Therefore, nurses are essential in the initial identification of any alteration in a patient's neurological condition⁷. The objective of this research was to examine the critical care nurses' knowledge of GCS in hospital critical care units. For critical care nurses, the GCS evaluation is a vital competency that enables them to monitor shifts in consciousness, diagnose neurological status fast and correctly, and coordinate the right therapies to maximize patient outcomes.

Methods:

A quasi-experimental study was carried out from July to December 2023 to assess the critical care nurses' proficiency in using the Glasgow Coma Scale in tertiary care settings in Islamabad, including the ICU, Neuro ward, post-operative ward, and Emergency department. The sample size calculation formula $S.S. = N/1 + Ne2$ was used to determine the sample size. For this investigation, a sample size of 60 was ideal. The total sample was $60 + 11 = 71$ when the non-response error was set at 10%. The nurses were chosen using the purposeful sampling technique. Self-Structure pre and post questionnaire was used to collect the data. Using Cronbach's alpha in SPSS, the instrument's reliability was assessed; the result was 0.78. Pretesting was conducted in four different settings of Islamabad hospitals among critical care nurses working in tertiary settings. The Rawal Institute of Health Sciences Ethics Committee in Islamabad granted ethical approval, and the tertiary settings granted consent for data gathering. The gathered data was checked each day before departure to ensure that all the information was correct. The obtained data was serially compiled in the file to prevent loss and harm. After the data was gathered, the questionnaire was reviewed twice to ensure it was accurate, relevant, and comprehensive. There were serial numbers assigned to every question. After the data were properly edited, they were grouped together based on the traits they had in common. These groupings were then used for the

analysis and description of the study's results. Each piece of information was coded after it was gathered. The correct response code was 1, whereas the incorrect response code was 0. Using SPSS-25, data entry and analysis were completed. The analysis of the data was done by descriptive statistics. Similar results were shown in tables, figures, frequency, percent, means, and standard deviations in descriptive statistics. The paired T test was utilized in inferential statistics to determine the relationship between the knowledge levels and other relevant factors.

Level of knowledge:

The ability of nurses to correctly answer 12 questions on GCS knowledge as stated in the instrument is defined in this study as knowledge of GCS. The maximum score for knowledge is 12. Four demographic questions, four experience-based questions, and twelve questions about GCS knowledge are all included in the questionnaire. A score of 1-4 indicates weak knowledge of GCS, 5-7 indicates average knowledge, 8-10 indicates good knowledge, and 11-12 indicates excellent knowledge. For every GCS component, there are four categories of knowledge: (0-33%), average (34-58%), good (59% - 83%), and exceptional (> 83%).

Results:

Of the 60 nurses, 11 were in neurology, 23 in emergency room, and 26 in intensive care unit. Thirty-eight nurses were female, and thirty-two were male. The majority of the respondents (40%) belonged to the 25-28 age range. Only 1.7% of nurses held a master's degree in nursing, compared to 58.3% who held a diploma in nursing and 40% who held a bachelor's degree in nursing. 36.7% had any kind of specialisation, and 63.3% were R.N. Approximately 60% of nurses had one to two years of experience, 26.7% had three to five years, and 13.3% had ten to twelve years. Table 1 indicates that 75% of nurses lacked any GCS training, whereas only 25% of nurses had any training at all. Table 2 has been discussed about mean, std. deviation, percentage and T text results.

Table: 1 Demographic characteristic of participants

		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex			
	Male	32	53.3%
	Female	28	46.7%
Age			
	20-24	21	35.0%
	25-28	24	40.0%
	29-35	14	23.3%
	Above 35	1	1.7%
Qualification			
	Diploma	35	58.3%
	BSN	24	40.0%
	MSN	1	1.7%
Job status			
	NOII	37	61.7%
	NOI	23	38.3%
	SNO	0	0.0%
	CNO	0	0.0%
Year of experience			
	1-2 years	36	60.0%
	3-5 years	16	26.7%
	6-10 years	8	13.3%
	Above 10 years	0	0.0%

As per the pretest questionnaire, 41.7% of nurses were aware of the original purpose for the creation of GCS. 35% of nurses were aware that an 8 on the GCS is considered severe. 38.3% of nurses were aware that patients with a GCS score of 8 or lower are thought to be comatose. Of the nurses, 55% were aware that the state of awareness of an intubated patient cannot be determined using the GCS. 53.3% of nurses were aware that narcotics could affect GCS results. 50% of nurses were aware that a male patient's motor response indicates that he is noncompliant. The maximum score for the verbal components of the GCS is 5, as 58.3% of nurses were aware. 51.7% of nurses were able to identify which area of the brain is being evaluated when measuring eye opening. 51.7% of nurses were aware of which area of the brain is evaluated when evaluating motor response.

According to the post-test questionnaire, 93.3% of nurses were aware of the original purpose of GCS. 91.7% of nurses were aware that an 8 on the GCS indicates a serious case. Of the nurses, 75% were aware that patients with a GCS score of 8 or lower are thought to be in a coma. 78.3% of nurses were aware that determining an intubated patient's degree of consciousness cannot be done using the GCS. 86.7% of nurses were aware that narcotics could affect GCS results. The maximum score for the verbal components of the GCS is 5, as 91.7 percent of nurses were aware. A total of 76.7% of nurses were aware of which area of the brain is evaluated when evaluating eye openness. 88.3% of nurses were aware of which area of the brain is evaluated when evaluating motor response.

Table: 2 Knowledge regarding the GCS scale of the participants

According to graph 1 of the pretest questionnaire, 25% of nurses had poor comprehension about GCS, 61.69%

Questions on Glasgow Coma Scales	Mean		Std. deviation		t	(Percentage %)		Compariso n
	Pre- test	Post- test	Pre- test	Post- test		Pre-test	Post- test	
The GCS was initially devised to	1.98	1.93	.770	.252	.454	41.6	93.3	51.7
The GCS score of 8 can be rated as	2.12	2.95	.825	.287	-7.284	35	91.6	56.6
Patient with GCS score of ____ and below are considered to be in coma	2.08	2.98	.829	.504	-7.469	35	75	40
The GCS cannot be used to assess intubated patient`s level of consciousness	1.45	1.23	.502	.465	2.428	55	78.3	23.3
Narcotic drugs will not influence the result of GCS	1.60	1.87	.558	.343	-3.128	53.3	86.7	33.4
On assessing a male patient`s motor response, he is unable to comply. You inflict a pain stimulus, and he pulls his arm away. what is his response category	2.23	2.15	.927	.360	.637	50	85	35
The maximum score for the verbal components of GCS is	2.13	1.92	.812	.279	1.857	58.3	91.7	33.4
What part of brain is being assessed when you are assessing eye opening	2.33	1.97	1.003	.486	2.609	51.7	76.7	25
Which of the option provided is the correct scoring of motor component of GCS starting from lowest	1.75	1.18	.914	.390	4.643	53.3	81.7	28.4
Which part of brain is being assessed when you are assessing verbal response	2.10	1.12	1.115	.324	6.273	36.7	88.3	51.6
What part of brain is being assessed when you are assessing motor response	2.40	2.88	.694	.324	-4.492	51.7	88.3	36.6
To test motor response in a tetraplegic patients (paralyzed in all four limbs), the nurse should	2.65	3.75	1.191	.654	-6.315	33.3	86.7	53.4

had average knowledge, and 13.31% had good knowledge. As indicated by graph 2, 20% of nurses had good knowledge and 80% had excellent knowledge following a GCS knowledge teaching session.

Graph: 1 Pre-test knowledge

Graph: 2 Post-test knowledge

Discussion:

This study explores nurses' knowledge levels and their ability to comprehend the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS). Initially the study found that nurses' knowledge was distributed in an unsettling way: 25% had low comprehension, 61.60% had moderate knowledge, and only 13.30% had good comprehension. This is in line with the findings of Teles et al.,⁸ who discovered that 74.55% of staff nurses had average knowledge of GCS and 25.45% had poor knowledge. Additionally, a different study revealed that a sizable percentage of nurses (51.2%) in the Adult Intensive Care Unit of federal hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, demonstrated inadequate understanding⁹ and 49/4% of poor knowledge in a study conducted in Abu Dahbi 2018¹⁰. The mean score for knowledge on the GCS was 5.5167 ± 1.50132 , according to our study, which indicated that participants had a moderate level of general comprehension. Similarly, research conducted in Lahore found that 65.70% of nurses had poor awareness and an unfavorable opinion of GCS¹¹. The findings of the posttest, which was conducted after focused study sessions on GCS knowledge, showed a notable improvement. None of the nurses demonstrated average or below-average knowledge on the posttest. Rather, 20% demonstrated a good degree of knowledge, and an astounding 80% achieved an outstanding understanding of GCS. In addition, the average knowledge score increased to 11.1833 ± 0.74769 after the intervention, indicating a significant improvement in the nursing population's understanding capabilities. The quality of patient treatment and outcomes may be improved by

educational programs aimed at improving nurses' skill in GCS knowledge and comprehension¹². The results of the study demonstrate that even though many nurses have a basic comprehension of the theoretical concepts that underpin the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), many of them struggle to apply these concepts in practical clinical settings¹³. Study sessions were found to be highly effective in improving the performance of critical care nurses and creating a positive opinion of the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS)¹⁴. Additional research is required and specialized teaching methods to fill up knowledge and practice gaps. In addition, maintaining and improving nurses' competence in applying GCS in clinical practice may depend heavily on continuous educational programs and routine evaluations¹⁵.

Conclusion:

Targeted educational interventions are required, as evidenced by the pretest findings, which show that a large percentage of nurses had poor or average knowledge levels on the GCS. On the other hand, post-test findings show a significant improvement following GCS knowledge instruction sessions, with most nurses demonstrating outstanding knowledge. This implies that organized learning programs can improve nurses' understanding of the GCS in an efficient manner, underscoring the significance of continued education and career advancement in critical care environments.

Limitation of the study:

This study may have limited the generalizability of the current findings. Additionally, the sample size of 60 nurses was insufficient to meet statistical

significance. Furthermore, there was a time restriction. Lastly, because this study was carried only in Pakistani hospitals in Islamabad, it could not be compared to studies done elsewhere in the world.

Recommendations:

1. It is essential to create and distribute a thorough handbook explaining the guidelines, specifically with reference to the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), to every nurse assigned to a critical care unit.
2. There is an urgent need for an educational program designed to improve nurses' comprehension and utilization of the Glasgow Coma Scale in critical care environments.

Conflict of interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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